

The HuT

Ongoing modelling activities in the Demonstrators

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1. Technical references

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1.1. Document history

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2. Table of contents

1. Technical references	2
1.1. Document history	3
2. Table of contents	4
2.1. List of Tables	4
2.2. List of Figures	4
3. Innovative Nexus Modelling	6
3.1. Weather & Climate Working Group	6
4. Activities in the Demonstrators' Arena	9
4.1. DEM1 - Valencia city, Spain	9
4.2. DEM2 - Val d'Aran region, Spain	12
4.3. DEM3 - Lattari mountains, Italy	12
4.4. DEM4 - Vilnius city, Lithuania	13
4.5. DEM5 - Schleswig-Holstein state and harbour cities, Germany	14
4.6. DEM6 - East fjords, Iceland	14
4.7. DEM 7 - Hungarian Tisza River basin, Hungary	15
4.8. DEM8 - Ogliastra province, Italy	16
4.9. DEM9 - Dorset county, UK	18
4.10. DEM10 - Bern canton, Switzerland	20

2.1. List of Tables

Table 1: Overview of stakeholder engagement in the ten demonstrators.	8
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2.2. List of Figures

Figure 1: A schematic of the warning value chain (from the WMO HIWeather Value Chain Flagship Project) showing the capabilities and outputs (green mountains) and information exchanges (bridges) linking the capabilities and their associated communities.	7
Figure 2: Projected maximum seasonal temperatures for climate change scenario SSP 126 (a) and potential evolution of heatwaves for climate change scenario SSP 585 (b) in the city of Valencia.	10

Figure 4: Procedure adopted to model surface temperature in the city of Valencia.	11
Figure 5: Hydro-geotechnical modelling approach adopted for multi-hazard (flood and landslide) assessment.	12
Figure 6: European Flood Awareness System data used to forecast triggering and predisposing conditions for flash flood and landslide occurrences.	13
Figure 7: Modeling stormwater runoff in the Old Town of Vilnius.	14
Figure 8: Monitoring network installed in the city of Seyðisfjörður.	15
Figure 9: Flood warning information shared with institutional stakeholders in the Hungarian Tisza River: mobile application Viz24.	16
Figure 10: Construction of climate scenarios: (a) fire size and historical frequency of wind direction, (b) six climate models analyzed for future scenarios.	17
Figure 11: Burning probability for a test area: (a) current situation, (b) most likely in the near future.	17
Figure 12: FLAM model has been calibrated to assess wildfire dynamics in Sardinia, focusing on burned area and fire frequency.	18
Figure 13: Case studies of multi-hazard events from storms.	19
Figure 14: Understanding signatures for improved warnings for landslides (a) and heat health (b).	19

3. Innovative Nexus Modelling

Several modelling approaches are being adopted for risk characterization in the ten demonstrators, leveraging the existing know-how of the project partners and using different data sources. The modelling activities in the demonstrators' arena have been defined considering modeling and risk analysis needs explicitly expressed by the main stakeholders in each Demonstrator. Considering that the starting point of each case study was very different, some demonstrators have been able to boost already existing consolidated expertise in these activities, while in other demonstrators The HuT is serving as a means of importing the best practices from other partners or more developed demonstrators.

Weather and climate forecasting activities are being carried at different temporal and spatial scales, in relation different variables, and considering the main gaps currently affecting model estimations in the areas of interest. The main overall objective of these activities is to device models that improve weather and climate forecasting for DRR/CCA purposes at local scale, and whose results can feed advanced predictive tools for risk assessment and associated impacts. To this aim, the specific characteristics of the demonstrators, and of the climate extremes and weather-induced hazards addressed in those areas, are taken into account. In some demonstrators, the modelling activities specifically aim at improving some predictive tools and approaches that forecast the potential impacts of extreme climate events. The improvement of such tools/approaches are related to either one or both of the following: short-term preparedness actions to be used in warning systems, medium and long-term estimates directing adaptation solutions to climate change.

3.1. Weather & Climate Working Group

The Weather and Climate Working Group (WG) has been set up to support closer collaboration between demonstrators, enable knowledge sharing on cross-cutting themes related to weather and climate, and support transferability of methods and solutions beyond a single demonstrator (a core aim of the project).

The Weather and Climate WG had its first meeting in February 2024. At that initial meeting the purpose of the working group was discussed. Several topics for discussion were identified by the participants. The topics spanned across the Warning Value Chain and therefore we've decided to orientate meeting sessions around key capabilities as shown in Figure 1. Topics that were pertinent to those in attendance included better identification and quantification of the impacts of the weather, early warning systems and effective use of meteorological data. There was representation from several demonstrators covering regions in the UK, Italy, Spain, Hungary and Switzerland.

Not all demonstrators are focused on the same hazards. The hazards of interest across those who attended our initial kick-off meeting ranged from floods and landslides, through to heatwaves and droughts. The participants are encouraged to suggest topics and challenges that they would like to discuss and share with the group. It is envisaged that the WG will operate throughout the life of The HuT project as needed and therefore will be able to cover a variety of topics over time. The utilisation of the Value Chain enables participants to prepare ahead of the meetings and ensures that conversations have some overall structure.

Figure 1: A schematic of the warning value chain (from the WMO HIWeather Value Chain Flagship Project) showing the capabilities and outputs (green mountains) and information exchanges (bridges) linking the capabilities and their associated communities.

Following our 1st meeting, the 2nd meeting (May 2024) focused on Hydrometeorological observation data that might be used in relation to the core hazards of interest to the participants. This included discussing the different types of observation data (e.g. in-situ sensors for point-based observations; satellite products that provide broader spatial coverage; novel observations (socio-economic impact data & citizen science) for non-hydrometeorological observations).

The 3rd meeting, scheduled for July 2024, then focused on the challenges and uses of different datasets for forecasting (predominantly for weather-related hazards). Within this discussion the role of capturing and quantifying uncertainty came up as a constant challenge across the participants. A 2nd theme that was highlighted as a core challenge, was the identification and assessment of appropriate data (i.e. the verification and selection of appropriate forecast data inputs for hydrometeorological applications).

Building on the discussions of the 3rd meeting, for the 4th WG session the coordinators invited two experts from the Met Office to present on:

- Gridded and Site-specific weather forecasts and post-processing [Speaker: Bruce Wright]
- Understanding which models are most appropriate to use in downstream forecasting application (e.g. for hydrological modelling) [Speaker: Marion Mittermaier]

A full outline of the meetings held by the Weather and Climate WG, together with their theme and the meeting recordings are provided in Table 1.

In addition to these meetings, in-person discussions amongst WG participants took place during the HuT Projects Annual Meeting. This was held in Switzerland between the 20th and 22nd November 2024. During these discussions, and reflecting on the October meeting, we identified a possible activity and/or hands-on training focused on model evaluation utilising the data available within Demonstrator 2 (Val d'Aran Region (Pyrenees)). This demonstrator is particularly interested in understanding precipitation-induced hazards and improving forecasts of potentially high-impact events. Understanding the key datasets and assessing their use and performance within a modelling chain is critical. We are now planning the 6th meeting (planned for March 2025) where we hope to scope this plan in more detail.

Table 1: Overview of stakeholder engagement in the ten demonstrators.

Meeting	Date	Content/Theme	Recording available
#1	23/02/2024	Kick-off Meeting: Purpose of WG	Yes
#2	24/05/2024	Hydrometeorological Observation data	Yes
#3	23/07/2024	Challenges of using different datasets for forecasting	Yes
#4	17/10/2024	Post-processing and model evaluation	Yes
#5	20/11/2024 - 22/11/2024	In-person WG discussions at the HuT Annual Meeting	No

4. Activities in the Demonstrators' Arena

4.1. DEM1 - Valencia city, Spain

The modelling activities related to weather and climate in DEM1 are aimed at: improving the forecasting capacities within the basin, downscaling the results, and trying new forecasting models. Dynamic exposure mapping activities are planned to be used as a starting point for the digital twin simulating heat stress mitigation measures. Improvements of tools that forecast the potential impacts of extreme climate events are addressing the following: drought and water resource management for the simulation of long-term climate scenarios with the aim of estimating the impact of climate change to the water availability and the raw water quality for the city of Valencia; urban morphology algorithms forecasting heat maps and urban heat island maps for the city of Valencia at a 30m resolution, downscaled from surface temperatures at 5km.

Some details on the ongoing modeling activities are reported in the following.

Concerning climate projections, the information from five climate models (GFDL-ESM4, IPSL-CM6A-LR, MPI-ESM1.2-HR, MRI-ESM2-0 and UKESM1-0-LL) has been processed for the three climate change scenarios (SSP 126, SSP 370 and SSP585), and then compared with observed data in the historical period 1979-2014. This activity allowed, among other things, to estimate expected maximum seasonal temperatures and the potential evolution of heatwaves in the city of Valencia (Figure 2). These climate projections are currently being incorporated to study the effects of different climate change scenarios also on water resources, droughts, and key sectors such as agriculture and the environment.

Heat waves modelling at urban scale is instrumental to develop an effective warning system for the city of Valencia. As such, the procedure adopted (Figure 3) to model surface temperature requires detailed analyses of heat islands considering urban morphology, as well as the spatial distribution of buildings and the population, with special attention devoted to vulnerable structures and people. Although the models present differences, compared to the observed historical data, all of them show that the intensity of heatwaves tends to increase, and the duration of heatwaves tends to be longer. Model results also show that the distribution of surface temperature is far from random, with spatial patterns around hot and cold spots, influenced by: city morphology, land use and materials, census divisions. Overall, the population in the most vulnerable urban areas lives with an average surface temperature of 1°C higher than the average surface temperature.

A drought forecasting operational service has been developed to provide seasonal projections of drought indices (6-7 months), in particular the Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI) and the Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI). For each index, four temporal aggregations have been considered (6, 12, 18 and 24 months respectively). These indices are used by the Jucar River Basin Agency to foresee future precipitation patterns and anticipate meteorological and hydrological droughts. In particular, the SPI12 index is explicitly included in the Drought Management Plan of the Jucar basin as an index upon which relaxation of minimum streamflows can be activated.

Drought indices are forecasted for the entire area covered by the Jucar River Basin Agency, based on open-access seasonal climate forecasts from the Copernicus Climate Change Service C3S (models ECMWF-SEAS5, MétéoFrance System, DWD-GCFS2.1, and CMCC SPS v3.5), combined with reanalysis observations of the last months from ERA5. Those forecasts are automatically updated at the same pace as the C3S (once per month), which is in line with the purposes of the indices. Once seasonal forecasts and ERA5 records for the last months are

collected, seasonal predictions of drought indices are computed using the standard calculation processes of those, based on pointwise cumulative probability functions previously derived from the ERA5 point historical time series. Seasonal forecasts, on the other hand, are post-processed against ERA5 data to ensure their adaptation to the climatic patterns of the area.

Once a new set of drought index forecasts is available, it is uploaded to a web platform developed in the context of the WATER4CAST project, funded by the Valencian Government (<https://water4cast-app.upv.es/>). A comprehensive skill evaluation is under development using the re-forecasts available in the C3S for the 1995-2014 period. Preliminary results suggest that 6-month time aggregations are skillful up to three months in advance, while 12 to 24 month aggregations show skill for the entire forecasting horizon.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2: Projected maximum seasonal temperatures for climate change scenario SSP 126 (a) and potential evolution of heatwaves for climate change scenario SSP 585 (b) in the city of Valencia.

Figure 3: Procedure adopted to model surface temperature in the city of Valencia.

Figure 4: WATER4CAST web platform with the SPI-12 drought forecast for the month of March with its forecast for the next 6 months, with the ECMWF-SEAS5 forecast system.

4.2. DEM2 - Val d'Aran region, Spain

The modelling activities related to weather and climate in DEM2 are aimed at: improving rainfall and soil moisture input for early warning systems addressing rainfall-induced landslides, debris flows and flash floods. Improvements of tools that forecast the potential impacts of extreme climate events are addressing the flood-landslide coupling model aimed at addressing cascading-compounding events simulations in Val d'Aran.

Some details on the ongoing modeling activities are reported in the following.

A coupled and ensembled hydro-geotechnical modelling approach is adopted in this DEM. The multi-hazard (flood and landslide) modelling framework has already been defined (Figure 4). Flood hazards are estimated based on thresholds of return period discharge, and landslide hazards are based on thresholds percentage of unstable areas. The proposed modelling system simulates multi-hazards suitable for snow-dominated regions, such as Val d'Aran. Ensemble modelling is implemented to improve landslide prediction based on machine learning techniques and physically-based models. Flood hazard modelling framework is based on discharge return periods and the results are compared with existing aerial photos of the landslide event in June 2013.

Figure 5: Hydro-geotechnical modelling approach adopted for multi-hazard (flood and landslide) assessment.

4.3. DEM3 - Lattari mountains, Italy

The modelling activities related to weather and climate in DEM3 are aimed at: improving the understanding about the simulation chains currently adopted for weather forecast; testing the usefulness of information freely available from Copernicus Services; developing nowcasting approaches to cover time scales not adequately considered by the regional early warning system. Improvements of tools that forecast the potential impacts of extreme climate events are addressing exposure mapping approaches for the quantitative assessment of risk over wide areas.

Some details on the ongoing modeling activities are reported in the following.

The analysis in this DEM are mainly exploring the potentialities of EFAS (European Flood Awareness System) data and re-analysis ERA5 data to support the regional early warning systems (Figure 5). Specifically, the values of volumetric water contents are being considered as proxies for predisposing conditions, to be used in combination with meteorological monitoring and forecasting data, within warning models for flash floods and landslides at territorial scale. Concurrently, the use of widespread exposure mapping data, at uniform and high resolution over wide areas, is being tested as a support for updating landslide risk mapping in the Campania region.

Figure 6: European Flood Awareness System data used to forecast triggering and predisposing conditions for flash flood and landslide occurrences.

4.4. DEM4 - Vilnius city, Lithuania

The modelling activities related to weather and climate in DEM4 are aimed at improving rainfall nowcasting and short-term forecasting. Improvements of tools that forecast the potential impacts of extreme climate events are addressing the impact of rainfall on the stormwater drainage system of the city of Vilnius, by means of expert assessment and numerical modelling, in close coordination with the municipality.

Some details on the ongoing modeling activities are reported in the following.

The analysis of the rainwater systems' drainage area in the old part of the Vilnius historic centre (UNESCO World heritage site) can help assess the impact of different rainfall scenarios, allowing to evaluate the adequacy or to pinpoint the main deficiencies of the drainage system in the context of a changing climate (Figure 6). The performed analyses can serve as an example for decision makers and can start the discussion on new planning projects and/or the revision planning strategies.

Figure 7: Modeling stormwater runoff in the Old Town of Vilnius.

4.5. DEM5 - Schleswig-Holstein state and harbour cities, Germany

DEM5 did not commit to actively working on modelling activities. However, concerning tools that forecast the potential impacts of extreme climate events, even if this DEM did not commit to actively work on modelling activities, the potential use of innovative exposure mapping approaches for the quantitative assessment of flood risk in the municipal area of Glückstadt is currently being explored. The current results are too preliminary to be reported herein.

4.6. DEM6 - East fjords, Iceland

The modelling activities related to weather and climate in DEM6 are aimed at improving the forecasting capabilities in the area of interest, which is characterized by steep high valley mountains in narrow fjords. Improvements of tools that forecast the potential impacts of extreme climate events are addressing: regional forecasting of landslides based on modelling of precipitation thresholds and soil moisture; local forecasting of landslides and avalanches based on improved precipitation forecasting on a small scale as well as analyses of weather leading up to former events.

Some details on the ongoing modeling activities are reported in the following.

Figure 9: Flood warning information shared with institutional stakeholders in the Hungarian Tisza River: mobile application Viz24.

4.8. DEM8 - Ogliastra province, Italy

Modelling activities related to weather and climate will not be conducted in DEM8. Improvements of tools that forecast the potential impacts of extreme climate events are addressing: adaptation and mitigation pathways reducing the impacts of fire events and related costs, analyzed in the short- and medium-term under a changing climate considering different management and adaptation scenarios; catastrophe models aiming at capturing how disasters related to fires unfold and impact insurable assets using sophisticated simulation methods.

Some details on the ongoing modeling activities are reported in the following.

The activities concern the development of two approaches. A demonstrator-level modelling approach is used to simulate high-resolution fire impacts under current and future conditions and to assess, with the integration of information obtained through stakeholder involvement, possible adaptation and risk mitigation strategies, including NbS. Figure 9 shows some results concerning the construction of the climate scenarios, for current and future conditions, used as input to the fire simulator. The simulation outputs include burning probability (Figure 10) and fireline intensity. At the regional level of Sardinia, IIASA's FLAM model has been calibrated for application over the entire island at 1 sq. km resolution. The model was calibrated and validated over a historical period 2005-2021 and show a good fit to the observation in terms of seasonal variation and spatial distribution of hot spot. Due to relatively high resolution, that spatial fit can be seen at aggregated level (Figure 11).

(a)

(b)

Figure 10: Construction of climate scenarios: (a) fire size and historical frequency of wind direction, (b) six climate models analyzed for future scenarios.

Figure 11: Burning probability for a test area: (a) current situation, (b) most likely in the near future.

Figure 12: FLAM model has been calibrated to assess wildfire dynamics in Sardinia, focusing on burned area and fire frequency.

4.9. DEM9 - Dorset county, UK

The modelling activities related to weather and climate in DEM9 are aimed at reviewing how to improve the pull-through of meteorological data from a range of timescales (nowcasting, NWP, sub-seasonal) to enhance impact-based forecasting. This involves identifying which models are most appropriate for which hazards, and user-purposes and then looking across the warning value chain to identify where they could be used more effectively to convey upcoming high-impact events to users. Improvements of tools that forecast the potential impacts of extreme climate events are addressing ensemble forecasts leading to different risk scenarios for improved decision making and warning communication.

Some details on the ongoing modeling activities are reported in the following.

Work is undergoing to understand weather feeds linked to the Warning Value Chain. Evidence for two storms both affecting southern coastal stretches of the UK has been collected (Figure 12). Both have been multi-hazard events with extreme winds, rainfall, and waves along the south coast, leading to wind, flooding, and landslide impacts. The analyses are focusing on finding relationships between meteorological and event data, towards understanding signatures for improved warnings for landslides and heat health (Figure 13). Concerning the case study, cliffs in Dorset county are considered to establish any relation between cliff collapse events and rainfall events. While at times this is the case, on other occasions wetter events do not trigger collapse. The approach is currently being refined to consider the different geological units within the area. Concerning heat health, the figure shows, for England and Wales, changes in the occurrence of different thresholds of heat warning. The initial analyses highlight that the spatial and temporal occurrence of these warnings is increasing. Future analyses aim to explore different elements including how the thresholds need to change to maintain current occurrences, using global warning levels.

Figure 13: Case studies of multi-hazard events from storms.

Cliff Collapse (BGS cliff and Met Office weather station data)

(a)

Heat Health (Using UKCP Regional – high emissions scenario)

(b)

Figure 14: Understanding signatures for improved warnings for landslides (a) and heat health (b).

4.10. DEM10 - Bern canton, Switzerland

DEM10 did not commit to actively working on modelling activities. However, concerning tools that forecast the potential impacts of extreme climate events, pathway schemes of cascading effects for the Zulg valley are currently being explored.

Some details on the ongoing modeling activities are reported in the following.

The well-established community-based early warning system in the Zulgtal may be enhanced by an automated system based on high-temporal resolution real-time precipitation gauges as well as combined model - remote sensing based automated nowcasting systems. Work is ongoing to evaluate the value added of high-intensity precipitation events and their spatial and temporal interpolation in the catchment scale by remote-sensing and model-based tools like INCA and 'Combiprecip' and the corresponding runoff-peaks of the Zulg river gauge of the Canton of Bern at Unterlangenegg, Chachelischwandstäg. Precipitation sums accumulated over several days and snow cover duration as derivable by MODIS satellite data will also be considered.

